

YOUTH SOCIETY IN NEW UZBEKISTAN THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THEATER ART IN INCREASE ACTIVITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12515695>

Abstract: In this article, as a component of the political and social system of the society, the aspirations of the youth for the perspective of tomorrow, their social actions, the processes of acquiring information, increasing social knowledge, and actively participating in the social life of the society are determined. The social activity of young people develops depending on the socio-political system of the society in which they live, relies on the skills, knowledge and thinking of the young people who make up that society, thereby revealing their social attitude to society.

Key words: Civil society, political-social, economic-legal, artistic-aesthetic, emotion, art, dignity, charm, passion, science and technology.

It would not be an exaggeration to say that the wide-ranging reforms implemented in the new Uzbekistan at a fast pace serve to increase the social activity of today's youth. Increasing the social activity of young people has always been considered one of the priority tasks in building a fair civil society. After all, only socially active individuals are able to build a legal democratic state and civil society. In the modern civil society aimed at improving the well-being of our people and further developing the social life of the population under the reforms, the main attention is paid to the social activity of young people. Civil society is primarily formed by active, free and independent thinking young people. In increasing the social activity of young people, it shows that the role of young people in various social groups, their participation in state power, political organizations, relations with other countries and nations, and the characteristics of social activity are formed in them.

Social activity - as a component of the political-social system of the society, determines the aspirations of young people for the future, their social movements, the processes of acquiring information, increasing social knowledge, active participation in the social life of the society. The social activity of young people develops depending on the socio-political system of the society in which they live, relies on the skills, knowledge and thinking of the young people who make up that society, thereby revealing their social attitude to society. The main goal of forming youth social activity in civil society is to expand the possibilities of the individual in his work, to strengthen the social and economic-legal equality and dignity of young people [1:955].

Civil society is a social space, and the law reigns in it, and does not hinder a person's self-development, but, on the contrary, helps him to realize his interests, to exercise his rights and freedoms as much as possible. The political and legal literacy of young people is the main criterion for the realization of the civic identity. By acquiring political and legal knowledge, a person should understand that he belongs to the country and society in which he lives. In the future, the citizen begins to understand the interests of the society and the state to which he belongs. It is noteworthy that the development of state and society is related to the political

and legal culture, participation and activity of the people. Let us answer the question "what does political activity mean?" Political activism is the participation of citizens in political processes based on their interests, following them and expressing their attitude to various socio-political institutes (political theories, representative bodies, social movements, etc.) or independently.

The following issues are considered important in increasing the socio-political activity of young people: imparting political and legal knowledge to young people. enlightening in a popular way;

formation of a database designed for easy and quick use;

political parties "youth wing", to strengthen the cooperation of relevant non-governmental organizations with educational institutions aimed at increasing the socio-political activity of young people in the formation of civil society;

support and encouragement of scientific researches dedicated to increasing the political activity of young people in the formation of civil society in the framework of socio-political sciences;

covering the issues of social adjustment and increasing political activity of young people in the development of civil society through mass media with the participation of relevant experts [2:94-95.] explained.

Today, attention and opportunities for young people serve to increase the social activity of young people. It is emphasized that the attention paid to the education system in our country is consistently continued, and that it is important for the development of society. In this regard, to develop a program for the development of theater art, in which to issue creative orders for the best plays, to improve the skills of creative and auxiliary staff in foreign theaters, and to establish an award named after Mannon Uyghur to support young directors. [3.] The role of theater art is considered to be of great importance in educating a person as a complete human being and in deepening his consciousness and thinking. Theater (Greek "spectacle" is a genre of art that conveys ideas to the audience through a scene performed by one or more actors in a limited space [4:1]. Art calls people to virtue, encourages goodness, the most beautiful feeling Humanity has entered the 21st century with a world of knowledge and highly developed scientific and technological achievements Art is one of the forms of social consciousness and is based on this analysis. Art is closely related to the development of social life. went

In the course of its development, art is not free from the influence of social stratification. The ratio of the struggle of social forces with different goals and interests, pluralistic aspirations aimed at stabilizing certain aesthetic dreams and hopes, protection or denial of existing social relations, the struggle of goals and interests affects the worldview of the artist, the artistic policy of the ruling circles, all these are the worldview, position of the artist, the principles of artistic perception of reality can cause the nature of art in general to be extremely delicate, extremely complex.

When an artist creates, a complex, conflicting, attractive, passionate scene of life unfolds in front of him. All types of art work on an equal basis, they are fundamentally different from each other in terms of reflecting specific aspects of individuality, satisfying specific artistic and aesthetic needs of a person. Types of art differ in terms of fulfilling social tasks. For example, the cognitive function of art manifests its own qualities in fiction and other types

related to it. Music forms the culture of personal feelings, visual arts promote the culture of observation through spectacle, open stage (variety) and circus arts are entertainment.

Just as art forms cannot replace each other, their development has historically followed unevenly. In different historical periods, in the life of different peoples, one or another type of art, which determined the artistic image of its time, was the leader. All types of art were developed in ancient Greece. From the beginning of the Central Asian Renaissance, the poetry and architectural fields of artistic culture rose to the peak of prosperity. While Europe flourished more in the visual arts during the Renaissance, the theater flourished in England.

Theater is not just an ordinary theater, but a place of education, culture, spirituality and enlightenment. Theater is one of the most epistemologically bright genres of art. Spectator is a place where a performance is shown, a space and a field where a performance is performed, which surprises, makes the audience think, and invites to wide observation. There are many types of art in this field: pop art, film art, visual art, status art, gifting art, folk art, but none of them can replace the theater. The reason is that only the theater communicates, speaks and thinks with the audience through characters and talented actors. There are definitions that this unique form of art - theater began in the East. The possibilities of reviving the possibilities of distinguishing between the honest and the impure, good and bad, day and night, black and white, good and bad through the characters are the colors of the theater performances of Central Asia (Central Asia), China, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Burma, Vietnam. Its popularity later led to the spread of theater art throughout the world. This rare art form - theater, which appeared in India in the century BC, has gone through a great development [5:173].

To study, enrich and promote the traditions of performing arts that have been living in Uzbekistan for centuries, to develop theater art in all aspects, to further strengthen its material and technical basis, to ensure the active participation of theater personalities in the spiritual and educational reforms being implemented in our country, to create an artistic complex that glorifies national and universal values. to create stage works, to improve the special education system in accordance with the requirements of the times, to fully satisfy the need for highly qualified personnel, considering that theater art is one of the powerful means of raising spirituality and enlightenment, to consistently implement the tasks related to the development of this art [6.] improvement and implementation are underway.

The decision of the head of our state dated November 28, 2018 "On approving the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the decree dated May 28, 2020 "On measures to further increase the role and influence of culture and art in the life of society" are related to the issues of developing theaters and increasing public interest in theater art attention was paid, priority tasks in the field were defined, a number of effective works were carried out in order to ensure the execution of these tasks. In particular, the websites of all theaters were updated and managed in three languages. each creative team stages about 150-160 new plays in the theaters of our republic, usually 4 per year according to the approved plan. The repertoire of creative teams includes examples of world and Uzbek classical works in the genres of tragedy, drama, comedy, intended for audiences of different ages and interests. The President expressed great confidence in us creative people and said, "Creative minds are the engineers of the human heart." When we dedicate ourselves to our work and create, we find a way to people's hearts. Theater art never gets old. No matter how much a person gets used to information technology such as

telephone, internet and computer, the role of the theater as an example of spirituality is different. Therefore, we should put on stage productions that raise the morale of young people, and involve our people, especially young people, in them[7.]. When we say theater, first of all, it is necessary to understand a large type of art. At the same time, theater is a spectacle, a performance itself. In promoting the beautiful qualities of humanity, the influence of stage productions is extremely powerful. Theater art reflects life, events, various struggles and conflicts, inner experiences in dramatic actions, through actor's performance. As long as there is a theater, life is fun and beautiful! In fact, the theater is considered a mirror of life, a holy shrine. And the lessons learned by him continue to encourage people to be humane. According to one of the founders of Uzbek theater, Makhmudhoja Bekhbudi, "The theater is a classroom." He was called to raise the morale of the people by staging his drama "Padarkush". In fact, the artistic people of this ancient world discovered the place of education, the so-called library, very long ago[8.].

It is known that theater is a lively, highly effective and ancient art. Its first elements date back to primitive times before our era. A performance art appeared, in which people who were interested in it expressed their admiration and feelings in various ways and imprinted on objects such as stones and fabrics. Archeological findings found in the territories of our country, information from several sources complement our opinions in this regard. We know that at the beginning of the 20th century, the laying of the foundation stone for professional theater by our intellectuals such as M. Behbudi, A. Avloni, H. Niyazi stimulated the development of many professions in this field. In particular, there is no mistake if the field of Uzbek theater studies is measured by the age of the theater. The field of theater studies is a science that studies the history and theory of theater, and the emergence of this science is explained by the writings of a number of enlightened intellectuals who were amazed by European theaters and performances. Intellectuals who came into the public eye at that time were in cities like Petersburg and Moscow, watched many performances and published their impressions and surprises in the timely press. From their comments, it can be seen that there is a desire to understand the difference between the professional European theater and the national traditional Uzbek theater and strive to eliminate this difference [9].

Based on the above points, it is worth noting that theater art has an incomparable power to give spiritual and spiritual nourishment to a person and influence his spirituality. The role and importance of theater art in increasing the social activity of young people. It is very important to inculcate the unique rich spiritual heritage of our culture on the mind and social life of today's youth

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